

THE EFFECT OF METALS ON POLYMERIZATION

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The effect of oleates of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn on the peroxide-catalysed polymerization of styrene and methyl methacrylate in solution in toluene and *n*-butyl alcohol has been studied. Copper is found to inhibit the polymerization of styrene and strongly retard the polymerization of methyl methacrylate. All other metals have a small retarding effect which is generally more prominent in *n*-butyl alcohol than in toluene. Iron (ic), however, accelerates styrene polymerization.

The effect of metals and metallic compounds on polymerization has been but little investigated in a systematic manner. Such a study, however, is of interest as metals are used for fabrication of reaction kettles and also as metals are known to have a strong influence on many well known chemical reactions. The purpose of the present work is to investigate the influence of different metals on polymerization reactions. Mention is, however, frequently made in the patent literature on the influence of sodium and alkali metal compounds on butadiene, isoprene, etc., and on the use of metallic powder and container in connection with monomers, specially those connected with synthetic rubber industry (Burk, Thompson, Weith, Williams, "Polymerization", 1937, Chap. III; British Patents, 504; 734; vide Fleck, "Plastics Manual", 1947, p. 17).

As metals as such are insoluble, we have chosen suitable metallic compounds viz., oleates which are soluble in organic solvents. We have studied the following metals viz., Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn; these were chosen as they are the active transitional elements used as catalysts and also are the most common materials of construction for reaction kettles. We have limited ourselves to two monomers, styrene and methyl methacrylate, and studied them in solution in toluene and *n*-butyl alcohol (monomer : solvent = 1 : 6.5 by volume, approx.).

EXPERIMENTAL

Monomers.—Commercial styrene was purified by washing successively with alkali, water, etc., and distilling in *vacuo*. Methyl methacrylate was prepared by the depolymerization of commercial polymethyl methacrylate. This was washed as usual with dilute alkali and water, etc. and distilled carefully twice under a 16" vigreux type of column.

Solvents.—Baker's C.P. variety toluene was used as such. Laboratory reagent quality (B.D.H.) of *n*-butyl alcohol was distilled over drierite (CaSO₄) before use.

Metallic Soaps.—The metallic oleates were prepared by the usual method of double decomposition between dilute solutions of sodium oleate and slight excess of the metallic salts. These were washed several times with water until free from inorganic impurities, dried in a vacuum oven at 50°, and used as such without further purification. The metal content of the soaps was determined by standard methods of analysis.

Catalyst.—Benzoyl peroxide was prepared by the method of Gambarjan, (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4008). The product was crystallised twice from aqueous alcohol and dried at ordinary temperature. The sample was assayed iodometrically by standard method.

Polymerization.—Freshly distilled monomer, solvent, and solutions of catalyst and soap were mixed in suitable proportions and 5 c.c. of the mixture pipetted into dry 16 mm. pyrex test tubes with constrictions near the middle, which were previously washed successively with hot chromic acid, sulphurous acid, water, etc. The contents were frozen in liquid oxygen and sealed under vacuum at the constriction.

The ampoules containing the reaction mixture were then placed in a thermostat maintained at $80^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. After desired intervals of time ampoules were taken out and the amount of polymer formed was estimated gravimetrically after isolation. The polymer was precipitated from solution by adding an excess of methyl alcohol containing some hydrochloric acid (to decompose the soap). Unconverted monomer, catalyst and soap were removed with the alcohol and the precipitate was dissolved in benzene, reprecipitated with methyl alcohol, and dried in a vacuum oven at 50° before weighing.

Viscosity.—Viscosity of the samples of polymer was measured with an Ostwald type of viscometer of efflux time of about 180 sec. with acetone. The temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.005^{\circ}$. Intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$, was evaluated from an extrapolation of the plot of η_{sp}/c versus c , where c is concentration expressed in g. per 100 c.c. of solution, i.e.

$$[\eta] = \lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \frac{\eta_{sp}}{c}$$

Our results are presented below with reference to each soap separately. In some cases the full course of polymerization was not followed and data for only three hours' time are presented. For comparison we have generally utilised the yield for this period of polymerization time unless otherwise stated. The accuracy and reproducibility of the yield data are generally within one unit per cent and hence any effect within this limit or below 5% of the yield in the control experiment is designated as small. In order to obtain the effects under identical conditions, each experiment with metallic soap is accompanied by a separate control experiment without the added soap right through under exactly the same conditions.

Manganese

The results with manganese are presented in Table I; they are graphically represented in Fig. 1 and summarised below.

(a) *Toluene as solvent.*—For styrene there is a slight but definite retardation. Methyl methacrylate also suffers a small fall in yield.

(b) *n-Butyl alcohol as solvent.*—In this solvent the retarding influence is more magnified. Polymerization of styrene is retarded by about 38% and that of methyl methacrylate by about 33.5%.

It is to be noted that manganese retards polymerization of both the monomers to the same extent, being very small, if at all, in toluene and being quite high (about one-third decrease) in *n*-butyl alcohol. This magnification of the effect in *n*-butyl alcohol, as will be observed later, is a common feature of almost all cases we have studied.

FIG. 1

Effect of metallic soaps on methyl methacrylate polymerization.

Curve A—Control for B. B—Mn oleate additive. E—Control for Co. Co—Co oleate additive. (Toluene solvent for A, B, Co and E). C—Control for D and Mn. D—Ni oleate additive. Mn—Mn oleate additive (single point). (*n*-Butyl alcohol solvent for C, D and Mn).

FIG. 2

Effect of ferric oleate on methacrylate polymerization.

Curve A—Control for B. B—Ferric oleate additive (0.85%) (*n*-Butyl alcohol solvent for A and B) C—Control for D. D— Ferric oleate additive (2.1%) (Toluene solvent for C and D).

Iron

Data are presented in Table II and graphically represented in Fig. 2. The results are as follows:

(a) *Toluene as solvent.*—Iron has a slight accelerating tendency in the polymerization of styrene. In this solvent the effect is, however, very small. Methyl methacrylate polymerization is retarded to the extent of about 27%.

(b) *n-Butyl alcohol as solvent.*—The accelerating influence of iron on styrene is much augmented in this solvent, the yield being raised by 19%. Methyl methacrylate polymerization is, however, retarded to an extent of about 15%.

It will be observed that iron retards the polymerization of methyl methacrylate but accelerates the polymerization of styrene, and as usual, the effect is magnified in *n*-butyl alcohol. This shows that the effect of the additive is possibly to influence one of the vital polymerization steps e.g., the chain propagation or termination step and not a simple effect on the peroxide decomposition. It may be noted from Fig. 2 that the retardation in toluene is present as usual throughout the course of the polymerization, whereas in *n*-butyl alcohol, though of course with half the amount of iron present, the retardation is perceptible only after about 40% conversion.

Cobalt: (a) *Toluene as solvent.*—As will be seen from Table III and Fig. 1, cobalt exerts very little influence, if at all, on the polymerization of styrene and methyl methacrylate.

Nickel.

Data are presented in Table IV and graphically represented in Fig. 1. They are summarised below.

(a) *Toluene as solvent.*—Nickel has very small influence on styrene as well as methyl methacrylate polymerization. The variation between control and experiment is rather small and so does not warrant any positive conclusion.

(b) *n-Butyl alcohol as solvent.*—As will be seen in Fig. 1, retardation, though feeble, is much more marked here. For styrene it is 7.5% and for methyl methacrylate the value is about 12%.

Copper

Data are presented in Table V and some are represented graphically in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

(a) *Toluene as solvent.*—Copper exerts a profound influence on styrene polymerization. As will be seen from Fig. 4 there is an almost complete suppression of reaction as is evidenced by the magnitude of the fall in yield, which is about 95 per cent. For methyl methacrylate (Fig. 3), however, retardation is not so marked, being only of the order of 18%.

FIG. 3

Effect of copper oleate on methyl methacrylate polymerization.

Curve A—Control for B, C and D. B—Copper oleate additive (0.46%). C—Copper oleate additive (1.14%). D—Copper oleate additive (2.28%). (Toluene solvent for A, B, C and D). E—Control for F and G. F—Copper oleate additive (1.0%). G—Copper oleate additive (2.0%). (*n*-Butyl alcohol solvent for E, F and G).

FIG. 4

Effect of metallic oleates on styrene polymerization.

Curve A—Control for B. B—Zinc oleate additive (2.0%). [*n*-Butyl alcohol and toluene mixture (1 ; 1.4 by volume) solvent for A and B]. C—Control for D and E. D—Copper oleate additive (1.0%). E—Copper oleate additive (2.0%). (Toluene solvent for C, D and E)

(b) *n*-Butyl alcohol as solvent.—The strong inhibition for styrene in toluene solution is also maintained in this solvent. Methyl methacrylate is also retarded to a greater extent in this solvent (Fig. 3), the fall in yield being 45.8%.

In order to ascertain the effect of this strong retardation by copper on the molecular weight of the polymer formed, an experiment was conducted with 1/16 of the weight of peroxide catalyst as given in Table V. This reduced the speed of polymerization to 1/4 of former value at the initial stages, and two samples (one control and one with 2% copper oleate) were isolated after 13 hours of polymerization. The control had a yield of 56.5%, whereas with copper the yield was reduced to 36%. The intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$, of the two samples in benzene solution are 0.85 and 0.62 respectively. It will be observed that the $[\eta]$ decreases by over 27% by using copper as retarder. This probably signifies that the retardation is brought about by some interference with the termination process and not probably by reducing the rate of initiation. In this retarded reaction the rate decreased more than the molecular weight and this agrees with Cohen's observation on retarded reactions in general (Cohen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1057). This again points to the possibility of copper playing some vital part in deactivating the active centres in the chain growth process (Foord, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 48). Difficulty, however, remains as regards the nature of the chemical metamorphosis undergone by copper oleate

TABLE I

Effect of manganese oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer.	Solvent.	Catalyst conc. (g. benzoyl peroxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g./100c.c. soln.)	Time (hours).	Yield.	%Retardation. (3 hours)	
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.98	Nil	1	47.0		
				1	13.6		
				3	26.6		
				4	36.4		
				2.5	1	14.5	Small
					2	22.2	
					3	27.2	
					4	34.7	
Styrene	n-Butyl alcohol	0.91	Nil	1	22.8		
				3	49.6		
				4	49.6		
	Toluene	0.96	Nil	2.0	3	33.0	33.5
					3	15.8	Small
					3	15.1	
n-Butyl alcohol	0.96	Nil	2.0	3	14.7	38.1	
				3	9.1		

TABLE II

Effect of ferric oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer.	Solvent.	Catalyst (g. benzoyl peroxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g./100c.c. soln.).	Time (hours).	Yield.	%Retardation. (3 hours).		
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.98	Nil	1	14.6%			
				1½	22.9			
				2½	36.7			
				5	51.0			
				5	51.0			
				2.1	1	9.0	26.9	
					1½	15.3		
					2½	27.3		
					3½	32.9		
					5	43.2		
	n-Butyl alcohol	0.98	Nil		1	6.7		
					1	14.4		
					2	40.7		
					3	71.9		
					4	78.4		
				0.85	1	8.7	15.2	
					1	13.6		
					2	39.4		
					3	61.0		
					6	68.7		
Styrene	Toluene	0.96	Nil	3	15.8	Small (acceleration)		
				3	16.4			
	n-Butyl alcohol	0.96	Nil	0.8	3		14.7	
					3		17.5	19 (acceleration)
					3		14.7	
					3		17.5	

TABLE III

Effect of cobalt oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer.	Solvent.	Catalyst (g. benzoyl peroxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g/100c.c. soln.).	Time (hours).	Yield.	%Retardation (3 hours).	
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.98	Nil	1/2	4.9 %		
				1	13.0		
				3	33.5		
				4	39.1		
				5	46.0		
				2.5	1/2	4.6	Small
					1	11.5	
					2	20.5	
					3	34.3	
					4	36.9	
Styrene	Toluene	0.91	Nil	3	33.6		
				3	33.2	Small	
		0.96	Nil	3	15.8		
				3	15.5	Small	

TABLE IV

Effect of nickel oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer.	Solvent.	Catalyst (g. benzoyl peroxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g./100.c. soln.).	Time (hours).	Yield.	%Retardation. (3 hours)
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.91	Nil	3	33.6 %	
			1.4	3	35.1	Small
	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.91	Nil	1	22.8	
				3	49.6	
				4	49.6	
				1.5	1	19.8
			3	45.0		
			4	45.8		
Styrene	Toluene	0.96	Nil	3	15.8	
			1.4	3	15.1	Small
	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.96	Nil	3	14.7	
				1.5	3	13.6

which is apparently not a reduced form of copper, neither is it found in a combined state in the polymer, though such combination for benzoquinone was observed by Breitenbach, Springer and Horeischy (*Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 1438).

Reduction of soap concentration, as will be seen from the above figures, generally decreases the extent of retardation or inhibition.

TABLE V

Effect of copper oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer	Solvent.	Catalyst (g. benzoyl per- oxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g/100 c. soln.).	Time (hours)	Yield.	% Retardation. (3 hours).	
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.98	Nil	½	4.9%		
				1	9.9		
				2	26.6		
				3	35.8		
		4	48.9				
		2.28	½	4.4	18.4		
			1	8.9			
			1½	21.3			
			3½	36.3			
			5	44.4			
		1.14	½	4.0	15.2		
			1	9.8			
	2		24.1				
	4		41.9				
	5		46.6				
	6		46.1				
	n-Butyl alcohol	0.98	Nil	2.0	(vide Table II)		45.8
					½	3.6	
					1	11.5	
					2	24.8	
3					40.5		
4					38.0		
5					37.8		
1.0					½	4.9	17.6
					1	13.9	
					2	36.7	
0.98	Nil	Nil	3½	62.7			
			5	65.2			
			6	47.5			
			13	56.5			
			2.0	6	11.4	75.9 (6 hrs.)	
13	36.0	36.5 (13 hrs.)					
Styrene	Toluene	0.96	Nil	3	15.8		
				3	0.7	95.4	
				Nil	1	5.6	
					2	10.8	
					3½	15.6	
					4	19.0	
		2.0	2	0.78	94.8		
			3½	0.9			
		4	0.9				
		1.0	1	0.5	90.7		
			2	1.0			
		n-Butyl alcohol	0.96	Nil	3	14.7	
3	1.7				88.2		

TABLE VI

Effect of zinc oleate on polymerization rate at 80°.

Monomer.	Solvent	Catalyst (g. benzoyl per- oxide per 100 g. monomer).	Additive conc. (g/100c.c soln.).	Time (hours)	Yield.	% Retardation. (3 hours)
Methyl methacrylate	Toluene	0.91	Nil	3	33.6 %	
			1.6	3	34.1	Small
	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.91	Nil	3	49.6	
			0.38	3	47.1	5.2
Styrene	Toluene	0.96	Nil	3	15.8	
			1.6	3	15.8	Small
	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.96	Nil	3	14.7	
			0.38	3	11.2	23.3
	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol + toluene (1:1.4 by vol)	0.96	Nil	1	5.0	
2				9.2		
3				12.6		
			2.0	1	3.9	21.7 (1 hrs)
				2	8.3	9.8 (2 hrs.)

Zinc

Data are presented in Table VI.

(a) *Toluene as solvent.*—Zinc exerts no appreciable effect on the rate of polymerization of methyl methacrylate or styrene.

(b) *n-Butyl alcohol as solvent.*—Styrene polymerization is retarded to an extent of 23.3%, though for methyl methacrylate the retardation is small, being about 5%.

Since unlike all the metallic soaps studied, zinc oleate appeared to be only sparingly soluble in both toluene and *n*-butyl alcohol, it was thought that the lack of activity might be due to low concentration of zinc in solution. So an experiment was carried out in a toluene-*n*-butyl alcohol mixture in which zinc oleate is highly soluble. Styrene polymerization was retarded at the initial stages of reaction as will be seen from the upper pair of curves in Fig 4.

DISCUSSION

Though metals are generally observed to catalyse ordinary chemical reactions, we find that all the metallic soaps studied have a tendency to retard polymerization, the only exception being iron which produces a definite, though small, acceleration on styrene. The very small acceleration shown by nickel on methyl methacrylate in toluene solution is rather doubtful. The retardation by metallic soaps, though general, is in most cases very small. And in this respect copper stands out prominent from all the rest in producing a strong retardation or almost complete inhibition (Figs. 3 and 4). Our present state of knowledge about the mechanism of retardation and inhibition (Bartlett, Hammond, Kowart, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, Discussion, 1947, 2, 342; Rohrs, Staudinger, Vieweg, "Fortschritte der Chemie, Physik und Technik der Makromolekularen Stoffe", Bd. II, 1942, pp. 36-48), is that the added

substances either destroy or combine with a growing radical forming a stable one in participating in further propagation. Since the metals we have studied have the property of forming co-ordination complexes, it is not unexpected of them to combine with the free radicals formed in the reaction and thus produce the effects observed.

It is known that higher fatty acids, such as oleic acid, have very little or no effect on polymerization. Our observation that oleates of different metals do behave differently according to their capacity to retard or accelerate polymerization and that the effect in some cases is negligibly small, points to the same conclusion. The activity of metallic soaps is therefore ascribed to the metallic part of the compound.

As regards the influence of solvents in our investigations, two significant points deserve mention:—

(a). The polymerization of methyl methacrylate is faster in *n*-butyl alcohol than in toluene, whereas that of styrene is only very little affected. From simple considerations it seems probable that the carbon-carbon double bond in methyl methacrylate is more affected by the alcoholic solvent than by toluene owing to hydrogen bond formation between the carbonyl oxygen and hydroxylic hydrogen, such as $-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}=\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{O}}\dots\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{R}$. Such an interaction possibly results in polarisation of the double bond and consequent diminution of the energy of activation of the reaction concerned. Such an interaction between styrene and solvents studied is precluded from similar considerations. The above observations are corroborated by our work in diethylene glycol medium where the rate of polymerization is faster than in *n*-butyl alcohol (data not reported here).

Fig. 5.

(b). The effects produced by the metallic soaps in *n*-butyl alcohol as solvent are much more prominent than in toluene. Figure 5 illustrates this power of magnification. In *n*-butyl alcohol a comparative plot of the rate of polymerization for styrene with different metallic soaps is shown in Fig. 5. It will be observed that the sequence is more or less the same in both solvents. Within the limits of experimental error, the polymerization rates of the various metals except copper are crowded within a range of only one and a half per cent (between 15% to 16.5%) in toluene, whereas the same spread over a range of 9% (between 9% to 18%) in *n*-butyl alcohol, which makes it easier to distinguish their relative effect.

Determination of intrinsic viscosity [η] of the polymer samples including those obtained from the soap-retarded polymerization of the methyl methacrylate shows that [η] varies between 0.24 to 0.35. This shows

molecular weight of the polymer produced is rather small. It is also found from the viscosity data that $[\eta]$ for samples obtained in *n*-butyl alcohol as solvent is as a rule greater than those of otherwise identical samples in toluene. The fact that polymer is insoluble in *n*-butyl alcohol but is soluble in toluene may have some bearing on this observation.

An examination of our data suggests that a grading of the metals could be made in respect of their efficiency in retarding polymerization. The relative efficiency of the metallic soaps in this direction for methyl methacrylate and styrene in the two solvents can be represented thus.

Toluene as solvent :—(1) methyl Methacrylate
 $\text{Cu, Fe} \gg \text{Mn, Zn, Co.}$
 (Ni accelerates?)

(2) Styrene
 $\text{Cu} \gg \text{Ni} > \text{Mn, Zn, Co.}$
 (Fe accelerates).

n-Butyl alcohol as solvent :—(1) methyl methacrylate
 $\text{Cu} > \text{Mn, Fe} > \text{Zn, Ni}$

(2) Styrene
 $\text{Cu} \gg \text{Mn, Zn} > \text{Ni}$
 (Fe accelerates).

From the above series we find that copper stands foremost in its capacity to retard or inhibit polymerization of methyl methacrylate and styrene in both the solvents. Manganese also is somewhat effective and the rest retard polymerization in general, but the extent is small. Iron is conspicuous by its exceptional property of acceleration on styrene polymerization irrespective of the solvent. Examination of the order in which the metals occur in the series suggests that apart from the influence, of monomers the solvents have some role in determining the relative efficiency of a metal in influencing polymerization.

Variations of the amount of soap added show clearly (Fig. 3) that the magnitude of retardation produced by additives is definitely dependent on their concentration. It is to be noted that on halving the concentration of copper oleate, which inhibits the polymerization of styrene, the extent of inhibition is reduced by a definite, though very small, amount (Fig. 4). Due to insufficient data at our disposal, no attempt at formulation of a quantitative relation is made in this direction.

Lastly, a peculiar feature observed in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate in *n*-butyl alcohol must be noted. Under the conditions of our experiment a tendency towards a fall in the overall yield is observed after about 80 % conversion in the control experiments (Figs. 2 and 3) which coincides with polymerization time of nearly 4 hours. This tendency is also noticeable in the retarded reactions with copper or iron (ic) oleate as additive and in these cases the so-called maxima in the yield-time curve is reached after the same period of reaction, though of course at a much lower conversion (Figs. 2 and 3). It should be noticed, however, that this downward tendency of the yield-time curve is much less in

the retarded experiments than in the control ones. From the above observations it seems likely that some oxidative degradation or depolymerization of the polymer formed under the conditions of experiment (high temperature and high peroxide concentration) is responsible for this effect. Also it seems probable that the depolymerization process is retarded by the metallic additives which accounts for the decreased downward slope in the curves for the retarded reactions. This retarding effect on the degradation is expected if the mechanism of degradation of polymethyl methacrylate is a reverse polymerization, being a chain reaction involving radicals, as has been shown by Grassie and Melville, (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, Discussion, 1947, 2, 378).

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